

Autonomy supportive and Controlling behavior of Senior High School and Grade XI Students' participation in Class discussion in Ilocos Region, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

The study wanted to determine the relationship between teachers' behavior in classroom and students' participation in classroom discussion. To support the study, theory was proposed, and related literature and studies were reviewed. To carry out the study, statements of the problems were proposed, and validated questionnaires were used to gather the data. The study used descriptive correlational research design aided by fact finding inquiry to explain teachers' behavior and its correlation with students' participation in classroom discussion. The population of the study was composed of 300 Senior High School Grade XI students of Divine Word College of Vigan, Ilocos Sur and Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte. The study found that teachers' behaviors, particularly autonomy supportive and controlling behavior correlate to the students' participation in classroom discussion.

KEYWORDS: *autonomy supportive behavior, controlling behavior, classroom discussion participation.*

Rationale

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I. INTRODUCTION

Often, we hear complaints of teachers about students who cannot speak and who cannot answer questions during class hour. Teachers are desperate to hear words coming from students and until the end of the class, teachers do all the talk. At the same time, we also hear some good stories about students who are alive and vivid inside the classroom because of their participation in the class discussion. As a result of those situations, some teachers are inspired and discouraged to teach. Such experiences lead teachers to conclude that teaching profession is a burden, while some see it as an inspiration and a mission. Should we blame the intelligence? It may be true, but it may not also be true because there can be other factors that cause students not to speak inside the classroom. The problem of students' disengagement can either be from students' side or from teachers' side. Studies have been done along those concern such as Rashid and Zaman (2018), Mehdipour and Balaramulu (2013) and these studies showed that the behavior of teachers is the main cause why students do not participate inside the classroom. There are two kinds of behaviors that are singled out as the causes namely, autonomy supportive and controlling behavior. Teachers' autonomy supportive behavior appears in how they motivate students and provide a conducive environment for open discussion. On the other side, controlling behavior of teachers in which teachers do all the talks and allow few interventions from students. Such behavior is usually accompanied by rewards, praises and punishment when the students are able or not able to participate in the discussion. These two approaches may affect students' participation in the classroom.

The role of person in authority or teacher in this case, is supposed to motivate but often time the behavior is otherwise, instead of motivating but controlling. Teachers' job is supposed to be supporting the growth of autonomy of the students and therefore teachers should provide mechanism in which the autonomy is developed. But in many instances as we observed, teachers often use controlling method in motivating students. Thus, the concern of the current study, the researcher would like to see the effect of the two approaches or behaviors of teachers of Divine Word Colleges to the participation of students in class discussion.

The Objective of the Study : The purpose of the study is to identify dominant teaching behaviors of teachers in the Divine Word Colleges in order to provide information for the management to establish policies related to teaching approaches and for the teachers to see the positive and negative effect of their teaching approaches and consider changing their approaches.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Understanding Human Behavior : In order to understand teachers' behavior toward students, we need to understand the causes of behavior. To explore further, we borrow the concept from behavioral physiology and anthropology. This is not to problematize the two domains, but the concept can help us understand human behavior and the behavior of teachers toward students. Behavioral psychologist defined behavior as actions of organism in relation to themselves or to the environment. In other words, it is how an organism reacts toward the stimuli that comes from inside or from outside of the organism (Emakumara & Rainis, 2018, Minton & Khale, 2014, Levitis, Lidicker & Freund, 2009, Dugatkin, 2012). Stimuli is defined as any phenomenon that influences the movement or behavior of a living organism. Any changes in the environment cause the organism to react. Reaction is the behavior of the organism toward the stimuli. It is the effect of the stimuli. Take an example when you feel cold, you put on jacket or stay near the stove. Stimuli are classified as internal and external. It is called internal when the stimuli come from inside the organism. Example when a person feels thirsty, he/she drinks water. It is called external when it comes from outside the organism. Example when you see crazy man holding gun you run away. It is said that an organism reaction toward external and internal stimuli is instinctive or automatic and it is also learned, in the sense that sometimes reaction is automatic without thinking and animals also learn to react the way how they are taught to react. Instinctive reactions are innate in nature, while learned behavior is learned through repetitive experience. Learned behavior is a result of experience and therefore reactions or actions toward the stimuli can be modified as a result of experience (Starr & Taggard, 1992).

It is said that humans are also interacting with the environment and the same as animals, human reacts when changes happen in the environment. As animals, they can also react instinctively or automatically, and they can react through their learned behavior. Humans have been raised in particular context and they have been taught how to deal with certain problems. But the way how humans react may be a bit different from animal. As a self-aware organism, human reaction or human behavior as a reaction toward the stimuli may not exactly be the same with animals. Animals may react instinctively or automatically and through their learned behavior, but humans use their reason or intellectual capability to assess the stimuli. Often time, they assess the stimuli before they react and when they react, it is always influenced by their reason or their mind or idea toward the situation. But their idea is not independent of the culture of the society but is influenced by the culture. Abun (2017) argued that human behavior is influenced by their attitudes or views toward a certain object or problem. If the person views the object or the problem negatively, then it will also affect how he/she will deal with the object or the problem. According to Abun (2017) human behavior toward the object or problem can be: love, respect, care, domination, control or destroy. Supporting such arguments is the idea of the anthropologists. The anthropologist have been arguing that the behavior of a person expresses his/her mind or attitude and such mind or attitude is taught by his/her culture. Therefore, it is correct to say that the behavior of person reflects the culture, the beliefs or the values of the community, of the culture. Cultural differences explain the different behaviors of different people because it is culture that forms the mind, the views or the attitude of people toward certain object or problems. Along this line of thought, Donald (2002) argued that culture plays important role in our brain functioning and even brain structure. It is undeniably that cultures of certain place such as practices, values, beliefs are taught to children from young age and those will affect their attitude and these attitudes, beliefs, values are taken into considerations throughout their life in their decision making and how they deal with problems in their life (Triandis, 1994).

Social environment or culture does affect the brain functioning as Hofstede as cited by Brown (1995) explained that culture is the collective programming of the human mind that differentiates human beings from other human beings. Hofstede as cited by Brown (1995) argued that culture is translated into how people thinks, how people behave, how people perceives things and it is through their attitude and behavior one can be identified where they come from. In relation to such concept, a study has been done by Amstrong (1996) to determine the correlation between cultural variables and ethical perception. His study found that there is a correlation between cultural dimensions and ethical perceptions. As Tangney et.al, (2007) later pointed out that morals affect the way a person behaves. In line with culture is faith. Faith is a culture that affects the behavior of human being. Faith is taught by their religion and religion has been considered as one of the most important factors of culture that plays significant role in shaping human behavior (Spilka, & McIntosh, 1996). The different aspect of cultures really affects the way how a human behaves and it affects how they look at the situation and what they expect to gain from it (Kecmanovic, 1969).

The Role of Teacher in the Classroom : Classroom learning environment is important factor in the process of learning and teaching. Teachers must ensure that the presentation help the students to learn and apply the concept.

Therefore, teachers should prepare his/her lesson and presentation (Cox, 2018). However, the role of teachers are not just simply to deliver knowledge. Though delivering knowledge is the main concern of teachers but such role can be hampered by classroom management. Therefore, to ensure knowledge sharing, teachers first have to follow the curriculum, committed to deliver the content by making a good preparation and presentation. Often time, even though teachers have followed the curriculum and made better preparation and presentation but if the classroom environment is not prepared for efficient and effective teaching and learning process, then it bounds to fail. Thus, it is one of the responsibilities of teachers to create a tone of classroom that is conducive for learning. Teachers have to make sure that there are no hindrances or classroom impediments that hinder the students to learn and to interact with the teacher and with one another. Conducive classroom environment is a prerequisite for teaching and learning to happen.

The classroom environment may be positive or negative (Ministry of Education, Guyana, 2017). Positive classroom means that students are happy to be in the classroom and they are free to interact with their teachers and their classmates. Negative classroom means that students are afraid inside the classroom because of fear of violating classroom rules, of teachers who are very strict, fear of punishment for not answering questions, etc. Negative classroom can be the result of lack of freedom of students in expressing themselves toward the teachers and toward each other. This is the challenge that teachers face in the classroom between letting the freedom rules the class and not letting the freedom rules the class and the relationship. The balance between the two priorities must be given attention because ignoring one aspect will also create a negative classroom environment. Consequently, from such complicated situation, the role of teachers today has evolved. It was used to be delivering knowledge only and therefore the concern of teachers was to master the method on how to deliver knowledge, prepare the lesson plans and prepare the test questions to monitor their achievement. Nowadays teachers are also acting as third parent (Cox, 2018) to counsel the students, support them, help them, motivate them or to inspire them to learn and apply it in their life. Failure may happen somewhere here. Often teachers are confused on how to balance their many roles, as teachers to deliver knowledge, as disciplinarian and as parents. Within these roles, teachers are in dilemma between applying autonomy supportive behaviors or controlling behaviors (Deci, Schwartz, Sheinman & Ryan, 1981, Deci, Connel & Ryan, 1989) or motivating style (Reeve, 2009). Often, teachers are mixing the two style at the same time, though the two teaching styles are separate. The two is separated because the two approaches bring different consequences to the students learning outcomes and even to the wellbeing of students (Cohen & Reeve, 2013).

Teachers' Behavioral Orientation : On this part, we discuss the concern of the study which is to investigate the prevalent behavioral orientation of teachers. The purpose is to help the teachers to know their prevalent behavior in teaching and motivating styles to the students and to know the advantage disadvantage of different approaches.

a. Autonomy Supportive Behavior: Autonomy supportive behavior is considered a motivating style of teachers toward students in the process of teacher-student interaction. It is a style applied by teachers to promote students' need for autonomy. It is accepted that teachers' teaching, and motivating style may not be purely supportive, but it may be highly supportive, and others are moderately supportive. However, whether is highly supportive or moderately supportive behavior, supportive behavior is necessary to improve classroom environment. The teachers' behavior during the classroom interaction must help vitalizes and nurtures and strengthens the intrinsic motivation of students to learn. Studies have shown that supportive motivating styles of teachers bring many benefits to the students such as higher quality motivation, greater classroom participation, higher quality learning, greater autonomous motivation, preference difficult challenges, psychological enhancement and physical well-being, higher academic achievement and experience positive classroom functioning (Reeve, 2016 cited from Cheon & Reeve, 2013, 2014, Cheon, Reeve, & Moon, 2012, Cheon, Reeve, Yu, & Jang, 2014, Reeve, Jang, Carell, Jeon, & Barch, 2004). Other studies have also reported that the benefits of autonomy supportive teaching style are not only limited to students, but it also benefits the teachers themselves such as experiencing higher satisfaction in teaching, and improving their physical and emotional well-being (Cheon, et.al, 2014).

Autonomy supportive teaching style can be shown by teachers through their teaching strategy and the way how they manage student-teacher relationship. Those strategies can be shown in a concrete form such as dwelling on the opinion of the students during the discussion, welcoming the opinions of the students and elaborate more ideas coming from different students, supporting students' initiative and competition, explaining the reasons behinds the rules, no imposition, providing options, opening two-way communications between teacher and students, flexibility, listening with understanding toward students opinion, welcome feedbacks and allow

students to work at their own time without being pressured by deadlines. The purpose of these strategies is to help students motivated in their study and learn something from their study and at the same time help the students to grow autonomously (Reeve, 2016).

The purpose of autonomy supportive teaching is to motivate students so that they can motivate themselves and become more engaged in classroom interaction. When the students are not under pressure or intimidation, they can be free in expressing themselves and be more open to the teachers in answering questions or expressing their opinions. Students would trust their teachers and would be more engaging in learning and can change their behavior becoming better (Kayufman & Sandilos, 2019). Ephancin (1994) contended that autonomy supportive behavior intends to encourage autonomy of the students for them to be able to manage themselves rather than being managed by their teachers. Further effect of such supportive behavior is improving relationship between teachers and students. Good relationship between teachers and students can have a greater impact on their academic and social development as pointed out by Birch & Ladd, 1997;

Klem and Connell, (2004) that teachers who have good relationship with their students produce positive effect on the students particularly on their academic development and motivate students to be more independent, more supportive and busier in learning.

b. Controlling behavior: Controlling behavior is forcing people to follow your way for the controller to be in charge of the situation. The controller does not want the situation to be out of control because it means that he/she cannot manage the situation and it may lead to destruction or failure. Though it is not necessarily bad because in certain aspect and circumstance such behavior may be required like in the military and even in the business. In fact, is one of the management functions. But it may not be good for teachers and students' relationship. In relations to teachers' behavior, control is the behavior of teachers who try to control students under their wings by pressuring students to think, and to behave according to what the teachers like (Reeve, 2009). Such behavior does not allow students' freedom of choice but always to subscribe to the behaviors that the teachers subscribe. Often teachers berate students on their path, and even use threats and ultimatums to tame students' behavior to follow their path. They belittle students and command their students to dress according to what they like and keep on reminding them about the dangers of not following their rules. They see to it that all students listen to him/her and behave properly in the class according to the prescribed rules that they made.

What is the purpose of this kind of behavior? It is not just to exercise power and gain personal gratification, but the bottom line is to gain students' compliance (Reeve, 2009) and to control victims in order to make them feel that they do not have an equal voice (Corry & McAndless-Davis, 2000). In relation to teachers-students relationship, often time controlling behavior comes in subtle ways in the form of positive reinforcement such as offering rewards when the students follow their teachers and perform well in the exam, giving gift, praising, flattering statement about the students, etc. It also comes through negative reinforcement such as punishment, threats or intimidation that would discourage students to make other actions that contrary to the wish of their teachers as Braiker, (2004) pointed out that manipulators and abusers control their victims in different forms.

The Idea of Classroom Participation

What is really a class participation? This study would define student participation in class discussion as active engagement process between teacher and students. This may include attending class and giving oral presentation (Fritschner, 2000), answering questions from teacher during the class (Burchfield & Sappington, 1999, p. 290) or students raise questions (Fassinger, 1995). Ideal classroom participation is expected when all students will involve in the discussion, will raise questions and answer questions (Wade, 1994). Classroom participation is important aspect to be established for teachers and students are learning from each other. Ideas are not monopolized by the teachers alone, but students too have something to share. By opening the wall between teacher and students then the flow of ideas from both sides can be realized. Through sharing of ideas, both sides can grow in terms of knowledge and views. It is through interactions, each student has the chance to learn through different viewpoints coming from different students and teacher on the same issue (The Teaching Center, n.d). Often time the teachers are surprised to hear different ideas from students related to the same issue at hand and it helps the teachers to be enriched and by doing so, both are learning from the interactions because teacher can learn from the conversation and students can learn to express themselves and build their self-confidence and autonomy.

Thus, it is one of the great responsibilities of teachers in classroom which is to motivate students to participate in the classroom discussion. It is one of teaching methodology that a teacher needs to establish. Along this line, teachers must find ways on how to inspire students who are withdrawing from class discussion and seem to be sleeping (Dallimore, Hertenstein & Platt, 2010). Beekes (2006) contended that motivating students to participate in class discussion is important to help the learning process interesting and to encourage deep learning to take

place. It is through interaction; students are encouraged to express their opinions and through such methodology students can improve their communication skills. Thus, one way that teachers can do to encourage participation is investigate cultural and educational background of students and adjust teaching strategy accordingly because Beekes argued that students from certain cultural background are often reluctant in joining the discussion as he pointed out that students from China, Far East and from UK presented different learning and teaching style (Beekes, 2006, cited from Cortazzi, 2002)

Teacher-students interaction always lead to positive outcome such as their cognitive growth, social and emotional development and well-being (Brazelton & Greenspan, 2000). It does not only enhance their skills but more importantly it enhances their self-confidence which lead to their autonomy. Teachers who create positive interaction will help the students to improve academic performance and professional development. Interaction between teachers and students may not be limited to formal interaction inside the classroom but even informal interaction outside the classroom. Studies had proven that students who had experienced positive interaction with their teachers likely to experience satisfaction in their college life and studies and would likely to further in their career (Rosenthal et al., 2000). This view has been strengthened by the idea of other researchers that teachers create great impact on the life of students in many aspects. Their interactions with the students affect their academic, emotional and social development (Hafen, et.al, 2015).

III. RELATED STUDIES

This part discusses related studies of other researchers regarding the research topic. There have been a lot of studies related to measuring the effect of teachers' behavior in the classroom, teachers-students interaction and the academic performance, social development and emotional development of students but there are few studies related to measuring teachers' behavior and classroom participation. Most of the related studies presented here are related to teachers' behavior toward students, teacher-student interaction which affect academic performance and emotional development. In relation to teachers' behavior and academic performance, Rashid and Zaman (2018) conducted a study to determine the effect of teacher's behavior toward academic performance of students in Islamabad. Their study had confirmed that teachers' behavior toward students had significantly affected the academic performance of students. The study pointed out particularly clarity, interaction, pacing, disclosure, speech and rapport were associated with the academic performance of students. Such finding had been found by the earlier study of Fisher, et.al (1981) that teaching behaviors correlate to the academic achievement of students. The similar study and finding were also presented by the study of Shah (2009) on the relationship between teachers' behavior and academic performance. The study further argued that students are more satisfied by the positive behaviors of their teachers. The same finding was also forwarded by Mehdipour and Balaramulu (2013) from their study on the influence of teachers' behavior on academic achievement of students. Specific behavior of teachers particularly teacher enthusiasm, teacher voice volume, teacher use of inquiries and teacher use of feedbacks were all related to academic performance of students (Ortiz, 1997). In terms of teacher's relationship between teachers and students, Shahmohammadi (2014) on his study found that teachers' behavior particularly receptive and honest relationship between teacher and students, self-regulatory behavior, respect and acceptance toward students cause the increase of self-regulatory behavior of students.

Regarding the effect of supportive and controlling behavior toward academic performance of students, the study of Hofferber, Eckes, and Wilde (2014) found that students who are taught by teachers who have autonomy supportive behaviors develop greater conceptual knowledge compared to students who are taught in a controlling environment. The controlling behavior of teachers were caused by the fact that teachers are responsible for the students' academic achievement and such responsibility leads them to be more controlling than teachers who have no performance standards (Deci, Spiegel, Ryan, Koestner & Kauffman, 1982). Such finding refers to what Reeve (2009) had found in his study that the reason for controlling behavior is because of pressures coming from above such as the dual burdens of responsibility and accountability. Beside pressure coming from above, there is also pressure coming from bellow such as teachers react to students' passivity during the learning activities and finally pressure from within such as teachers tend to endorse the maximum operant principle and sometimes because of personality disposition. Studies have also discovered that supportive autonomy teaching behavior lead to self-efficacy and intrinsic motivation and consequently self-efficacy and intrinsic value correlates to cognitive engagement and academic performance (Pintrich & De Groot, 1990). Thus, classroom interaction should promote cognitive engagement between teachers and students because it is only through cognitive engagement, students and teachers can grow in terms of understanding of the subject matter at hand. Along this line, studies have consistently found that classroom interaction affect academic performance as pointed by the study of Bolarinwa and Okolocha (2016). Similar finding was also forwarded by the study of Ameen, Hussain and Bakhsh (2011) on the effect of classroom interaction on students' academic achievement. The study compared the academic achievement of interactive class and controlled class. It was

found that interactive class perform better in term of academic achievement compared to the class that have no interaction. Other similar study was conducted by Kalu (n.d) on the classroom interaction pattern and students' learning outcome and the result confirm the previous findings that classroom interaction correlates to academic performance.

This is also strengthened by the finding of Allen, et.al (2013) that effective teacher- student interaction which is characterized by positive emotional climate, the use of diverse and engaging learning formats and problem-solving focus were associated with higher learning outcomes.

Conceptual Framework

Independent Variable

Dependent Variable

Figure 1. Conceptual framework explains the relationship of teachers' behavior toward students and its effect on participation in class discussion. Teachers' behaviors are independent variable and participation in class discussion is dependent variable.

Statement of the Problems

The study wants to determine the effect of teachers' behavior in the classroom toward students' participation in class discussion, specifically it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is teachers' behaviors in terms of
 - 1.1. Autonomy supportive behavior
 - 1.2. Controlling behavior
2. What is the participation of students in class discussion.
3. Is there a relationship between teachers' behavior and participation in class discussion?

Assumption of the Study: The study assumes that teachers' behavior affects the class participation of students and such behaviors can be measured. It is also assumed that the questionnaires are valid, and the answers are honest.

Hypothesis : Studies related to teachers' behavior and academic performance have been done and those studies found that teachers' behavior in terms of autonomy supportive and controlling behaviors affect the academic performance of students (Hofferber, Eckes, and Wilde (2014, Deci, Spiegel, Ryan, Koestner & Kauffman, 1982) and therefore the current study hypothesizes that teachers' behavior in terms of autonomy supportive and controlling behavior affects the students' participation in class discussion.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study: The study was limited to measuring teachers' behavior in terms of autonomy supportive and controlling behaviors toward participation in class discussion at the Senior High School of the Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Region. Research Methodology In order to carry out the study, an appropriate research methodology is utilized. Therefore, this part discusses research design, data gathering instruments, population, locale of the study, data gathering procedures and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design: The study is a quantitative study and uses correlational descriptive research design and aided by fact finding inquiry to determine the teachers' behavior in terms of autonomy supportive behavior, controlling behavior and participation in class discussion. According to Best and Khan (1993) descriptive research is to describe and explain what is found in the data. It concerns with conditions of relationship that exist; practices that prevail; beliefs, processes that are going on; effects that are being felt; or trends that are

developing. In other words, it describes the data that have been collected on research sample, describes “what is” about the data gathered.

Locale of the Study: The locale of the study was Divine Word College of Vigan, Ilocos Sur and Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, Philippines. These colleges are located in Ilocos Region, Philippines

Population: The population of the study was composed of all Grade XI Senior High School Students of these two colleges. Since the number of grade XI students were limited, then total enumeration sampling or a total of 300 students were used to meet the required data for the study.

Data Gathering instruments : The study utilized questionnaires. The questionnaires were adopted from Reeve (2009, pp. 131-132) on Autonomy Supportive Teaching. The questionnaires were distributed to all grade XI students of these private Catholic colleges in Ilocos Region. Questionnaires were composed of three parts and they are autonomy supportive behavior, controlling behavior and participation in class discussion.

Data Gathering Procedures : In the process of data gathering, the researcher sent letters to the Presidents of the two colleges in Ilocos Sur, requesting the Presidents to allow the researcher to flow his questionnaires in his college. The researcher personally met the Presidents and students and requested them to answer the questionnaires. The retrieval of questionnaires was arranged between the President’s representative and the researcher with the help of employees and faculty of the three colleges.

Statistical Treatment of Data : In consistent with the study as descriptive research, therefore descriptive and inferential statistic are used to measure the weighted mean and the Pearson r will be used to measure their correlations. Pearson (r) or Product Moment Correlation Coefficient is used to determine the strength of correlation between two or more interval and ratio data (Ariola, 2006).

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Interpretation	Overall Descriptive Rating
4.21-5.00	<i>Always</i>	<i>all the time</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Very often</i>	<i>most of the time</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Sometimes</i>	<i>often</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Seldom</i>	<i>rarely</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Never performed</i>	<i>none at all</i>

Findings: The following are the findings of the study and they are presented according to the statement of the problems of the study.

Problem 1a: What is teachers’ behavior in terms of autonomy supportive?

Table 1a: Autonomy supportive

Autonomy Supportive		
	X	DR
1. Respect students’ ideas in the discussion	3.86	Very often/most of the time
2. Incorporate inputs from the students in the discussion	3.42	Very often/most of the time
3. Provide interesting learning activities	3.72	Very often/most of the time
4. Support students’ autonomy	3.58	Very often/most of the time
5. Explain the reason why certain activity is done	3.61	Very often/most of the time
6. Explain the benefits of certain activity	3.63	Very often/most of the time
7. Provide options and allow students to decide on certain issues or problems	3.44	Very often/most of the time
8. Are flexible and open-minded to welcome new ideas	3.72	Very often/most of the time
9. Listen carefully with understanding	3.92	Very often/most of the time
10. Welcome complaints as valid	3.51	Very often/most of the time
11. Allow the students to work at their own pace	3.53	Very often/most of the time
12. Calmly wait for students’ signals of initiative, input and willingness	3.46	Very often/most of the time

Overall	3.62	Very often/most of the time
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Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>Always</i>	<i>all the time</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Very often</i>	<i>most of the time</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Sometimes</i>	<i>often</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Seldom</i>	<i>rarely</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Never</i>	<i>not at all</i>

Based on the presented data as reflected on the table, it shows that as a whole, teachers' behavior in terms of autonomy supportive is considered very often or most of the time as it is indicated by its weighted mean of 3.62. In other words, most of the time, teachers support the autonomy of the students. Taking it singly, all questions were also evaluated within the same range of value with the same interpretation that teachers respect students' ideas (3.86), provide options and allow students to decide on certain issues or problems (3.44), incorporate inputs from the students in the discussion (3.42), support students' autonomy (3.58), explain the reason why certain activity is done (3.61), explain the benefits of certain activity (3.63), are flexible and open-minded to welcome new ideas (3.72), listen carefully with understanding (3.92), welcome complaints as valid (3.51), allow the students to work at their own pace (3.53), calmly wait for students' signals of initiative, input and willingness (3.46) and provide interesting learning activities (3.72).

Problem 1b: What is teachers' behavior in terms of controlling behavior?

Table1b: Controlling Behavior

Controlling behavior	X	DR
	X	DR
1. Impose their own plans to students	3.41	Very often/most of the time
2. Are not responsive to students' needs	2.93	Sometimes/often
3. Demand compliance	3.15	Sometimes/often
4. Offer rewards to students who comply	3.03	Sometimes/often
5. Directive without explanation	3.03	Sometimes/often
6. Request to do certain assignment without explanation	3.04	Sometimes/often
7. Use pressuring language to do certain task or assignment	3.05	Sometimes/often
8. Explain in detail what to do with certain task or assignment	3.43	Very often/most of the time
9. Often raise their voice to convey their message	3.27	Sometimes/often
10. Counter and argues against the students' ideas	3.01	Sometimes/often
11. Pushes students to produce right answers	3.24	Sometimes/often
12. Communicate what is right and push the students to produce it quickly	3.19	Sometimes/often
Overall	3.15	Sometimes/often

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>Always</i>	<i>all the time</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Very often</i>	<i>most of the time</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Sometimes</i>	<i>often</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Seldom</i>	<i>rarely</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Never</i>	<i>not at all</i>

When it comes to controlling behavior, the result indicates that teachers are more supportive to the autonomy of the students than controlling the students as it is indicated by its data as reflected on the table that as a whole, controlling behavior of teachers are considered "sometimes" or "often" with its mean value of 3.15 which is interpreted as often or sometimes. It is lower than autonomy supportive behavior. They are not very often using controlling behavior in the classroom. It means that only sometimes teachers apply controlling behavior in their dealing with the students. Even when the questions are taken singly, it would fall within the same range of interpretation as often or sometimes. Teachers sometimes or often demand compliance (3.15), offer rewards to

students who comply (3.03), are not responsive to students' needs (2.93), are telling students to do something without direction (3.03), are requesting students to do certain assignment without explanation (3.04), are using pressuring language to do certain assignment or task(3.05), are explaining in details what to do with certain task (3.43), are raising their voice to convey their message (3.27), and they often counter and argue with the students' idea (3.01), push students to produce the right answer (3.24), and communicate what is right and push students to produce ideas quickly (3.19).

Problem 2: What is classroom participation of the students?

Table2: Classroom participation

Classroom Participation		
	X	DR
1. I answer questions from teacher	3.37	Sometime/often
2. I raise questions to the teachers when I do not understand the explanation	3.10	Sometime/often
3. I am prepared to argue with the ideas of my teachers	2.76	Sometime/often
4. I am always excited to attend my class	3.55	Very often/most of the time
5. If I am confused with certain thing, I do not hesitate to ask for clarification from my teachers	3.48	Very often/most of the time
Overall	3.25	Sometime/often

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Always	all the time
3.41-4.20	Very often	most of the time
2.61-3.40	Sometimes	often
1.81-2.60	Seldom	rarely
1.00-1.80	Never	not at all

As it is gleaned from the data collected as presented on the table, it reveals that, as a whole, students are often participating in classroom discussion. They are not very often or not always participating in classroom discussion as reflected by its mean value of 3.25 as interpreted as often or sometimes. Taking it singly, students often answer questions from teachers (3.37), often raise questions to the teachers when they do not understand (3.10), often prepared to argue with the idea of their teachers (2.76). There were two questions that were answered very often or most of the time by the students in terms of classroom participation, that students are excited to attend class (3.55) and when they are confused, they raised questions to their teachers (3.48).

Problem 3: Is there a relationship between teachers' behavior and participation in classroom discussion?

Table 3: Correlation

Correlation	
autonomy	0.4338*
controlling	0.2786*
As a whole	0.3562*

*Significant at .05 level (2 – tailed)

When it comes to the relationship between teachers' behavior and students' participation in classroom discussion, the results indicate that as a whole, there is a significant relationship between teachers' behavior and students' participation in classroom discussion as reflected by its correlation value of 0.3562* which is higher than .05 (2-tailed) level of significance. Taking it singly, autonomy correlates to the students' participation in classroom discussion and controlling behavior also correlates to the class discussion participation of the students.

V. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that teachers' autonomy supportive behavior is higher than teachers' controlling behavior. Whatever teachers' behavior in dealing with the students in the classroom affect students' participation in classroom discussion, whether they apply autonomy supportive behavior or controlling behavior. Recommendation Teachers should apply autonomy supportive behavior when they try to inspire students' participation in classroom discussion.

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